

PROTOCOL BRIEF

REVIEW TITLE

Capacity Building Frameworks in Health Research: A Scoping Review

TEAM INFORMATION

Project Lead & Corresponding Author

Annie LeBlanc

Team Members (in alphabetical order)

Bergeron, Frédéric	Goldowitz, Daniel	Pritchard-Wiart, Lesley
Bosma, Rachael	Grenier, Emilie	Rojas, David
Buckreus, Kelli	Jin, Jenny	Samuel, Susan
Colquhoun, Heather	Langlois, Léa	Stéfan, Théo
Demers, Juliette	L'espérance, Audrey	Tchernof, André
DeMore, Jamie	Pelling, Yvonne	Tricco, Andrea C.
Fernandez, Nicolas	Poirier, Marie-Dominique	Witteman, Holly
Gaboury, Isabelle	Poitras, Marie-Eve	

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BACKGROUND

Capacity building in health research remains poorly defined, with contradictions and confusion in its conceptualization and operationalization despite substantial investments and broad recognition of its importance.¹⁻⁴ Capacity building in research generally refers to intertwined mechanisms or efforts to develop, enhance or strengthen the abilities of individuals, teams, organizations and systems to undertake, disseminate, and sustain high quality research efficiently and effectively.^{1,5,6} Models or frameworks produced over the years have addressed various dimensions (e.g., competencies, infrastructures) and principles, across structural levels (e.g., individuals, organizations), generally within a specific health discipline, using a large variety of measures to assess needs, development, monitoring or impact.^{5,7-10} This lack of cohesion impedes comparability, transferability, and replicability of results with direct consequences on our understanding of the relationship between capacity building efforts and health outcomes.¹⁰ Furthermore, few frameworks have addressed the core values of health research and care that are the involvement of patients and the consideration of their experiential knowledge, and the integration of equity, diversity and inclusion principles, and cultural safety.

OBJECTIVES

To synthesize the body of evidence (e.g., definitions, concepts, principles, models, frameworks, theories, efforts, impact) on capacity building in health research. More specifically: (i) What evidence is available that defines or describes concepts, principles, models, or frameworks of capacity building in health research? (ii) What are methodologies and substantive theories related to capacity building in health research? (iii) What level of evidence is available that reports on capacity building efforts and impact in health research?

PATIENT AND PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT

Knowledge users (e.g., patients, healthcare professionals, decision-makers) involved in networks dedicated to building research capacity in their respective field were and will continue to be involved throughout the preparation, governance, and conduct of the review, and dissemination of its findings.

DESIGN

We will conduct a scoping review following the methodological steps outlined by Arksey & O'Malley and refined by the JBI and report our findings according to the PRISMA-ScR 2020 Guideline and extension for scoping reviews.¹¹⁻¹³

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA & SEARCH STRATEGIES

Eligibility criteria according to the Population, Concept, Context, and Types of Evidence Sources Framework are as followed:

PCC Criteria	Inclusion	Definition or justification
Population	Target, end-user, and knowledge users	Any target, end-user or knowledge users of capacity building efforts (e.g., patients/ citizens, health care professionals, health care organizations, managers, researchers and research organizations)
Concept(s)	Capacity building	Capacity building (interchangeably referred to as capacity strengthening or capacity development) defined as: mechanisms or efforts to “develop, enhance or strengthen the abilities of individuals, teams, organizations and systems to undertake and disseminate high quality research efficiently and effectively”.
	Frameworks	Framework, theory, model, concepts or principles, defined as a set of notions, a relational structure or a conceptual representation of capacity building, strengthening or development.
Context	Any health research setting	<p>Research in health, such as:</p> <p>The capacity building framework (or equivalent) is about or has been applied toward building capacity for research in a domain within the health/healthcare/social service context (e.g., Capacity building principles in primary health care research, or a framework that focused on capacity building in education research but has been applied and used in the context of cancer research); OR</p> <p>The capacity building framework (or equivalent) is about or has been applied toward building capacity for research for individuals/populations associated with health/healthcare/social service context (e.g., Framework to develop research capacity for allied health, or a capacity building framework for manager applied for research team leaders).</p>
Evidence sources	Published and unpublished literature	Primary and secondary research using any study designs and data collection methods, including knowledge synthesis; theses, dissertations, and perspective articles (conceptual and methodological); government, academic or clinical reports, manual and guidelines; and books.

We will co-develop and test search strategies in key major databases using an iterative process under the leadership of an experienced medical information specialist, which will be peer-reviewed by an independent information specialist using the PRESS Checklist.¹⁴ We will develop a search strategy for unpublished or grey literature to identify additional documentation.¹⁵

DATA SELECTION & EXTRACTION

Pairs of reviewers will independently screen titles and abstracts first, then full texts to determine eligibility of the retrieved citations. We will conduct pilot testing of the standardized screening forms for each level of screening, with all reviewers. We will co-develop a standardized extraction form, one that includes data related to knowledge users' engagement, equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) including sex and gender, and cultural safety, which will be pilot tested by all reviewers. Data extraction will be performed by pairs of reviewers with no two junior reviewers ever paired together. Senior reviewers with capacity building expertise will verify random samples of data to ensure high quality data charting.

Disagreements will be resolved by consensus and, if needed, consultation with a third, senior reviewer. Where required, authors will be contacted for missing or additional data.

STUDY QUALITY ASSESSMENT

We will not conduct quality/risk of bias assessment of the selected studies considering the nature of the research questions and data extracted.

DATA SYNTHESIS

We will establish lists and areas of consensus regarding definitions, concepts, principles, models, and frameworks, as well as found methodologies and substantives theories. We will document inclusion of Knowledge users' engagement, EDI, and cultural safety. We will map together subsets of frameworks and associated features.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

Following this review, we should have (i) an expanded, comprehensive definition of capacity building and the extent to which principles of patient engagement, EDI, and cultural safety has been taken into consideration, (ii) a mapping of overlapping concepts and principles, models, and frameworks, (iii) an initial body of evidence documenting capacity building efforts and impacts.

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